

BURIAL RITUALS AMONG IBIL PEOPLE IN OGOJA, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The commemoration of the deceased is a widely embraced cultural tradition within the Ibil Ogoja Community located in Cross River State. The deceased are regarded with profound respect, as they are thought to maintain a unique connection with the living. This study investigated the rites and embodied ritual practices related to burial within the Ibil Ogoja community. The research was founded on Ritual Theory. An ethnographic research design was employed for the study, utilising in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and observational techniques for data collection. Participants were selected through purposive sampling for the study. Interview guide was used as instrument for data collection. Thematic analysis was conducted to interpret the narratives provided by the participants, aiming to answer the research questions. The findings indicated the Ibil Ogoja people do engaged in several ritual as rites for the dead to transit from the land of the living to the ancestral world. These rituals convey several cultural purposes like economic and social to the Ibil Ogoja people. The study concludes that, the rituals linked to burial within the community signify a collective action aimed at returning the deceased to Mother Earth while providing solace to those who mourn. Consequently, it is recommended that community members capitalise on the substantial investment opportunities arising from the celebration of the dead, the government should regulate ritual practices among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State especially, elements that intensify financial and social challenges.

Keywords: Rituals, Celebration of the dead, Burial, and Ibil Ogoja people

Scholars such as Olupana (2014) and Wilson *et al.* (2023) suggest that African societies are characterised by rich and diverse cultures that influence individuals' behaviour across all facets of life. Nigeria is recognised as one of the most culturally diverse nations in Africa, home to over 250 ethno-national groups (Bankole, 2013). This rich cultural heritage encompasses values, belief systems, festivals, and ceremonies (Adekiya, 2016). Consistent with the perspectives of functionalists, efforts to comprehend cultural elements should be rooted in a profound understanding of their roles within the societal context (Darnell, 2013).

Across the globe, even dating back to prehistoric times, concepts surrounding death, the afterlife, and the quest for a coherent understanding of these two ideas have engaged human contemplation since our earliest history (Despider and Strickland, 2011). Humanity has been intrigued by death for ages and has endeavoured to reconcile with its inevitability. This fascination arises from the fact that death disrupts the harmony and unity within families and communities more profoundly than any other event (Okeja, 2006). Even more unsettling is the reality that death does not discriminate based on age, gender, or social status. As death signifies both the end of the physical form and the erasure of social identity, a prevalent

reaction to the contemplation of it is fear. In this context, the bereavement of a loved one due to death is an emotionally distressing ordeal that evokes fear and diminishes feelings of safety, which can, in certain instances, result in mood fluctuations, depression, and erratic behaviour (Alkozei *et al.*, 2019; Jordan and Litz, 2014; Keyes *et al.*, 2014).

Across the globe, ritualized ceremonies referred to as rites of passage are conducted to honour the natural transitions that all humans undergo (Nwadiokwi *et al.*, 2016). The groundbreaking research by Gennep (1960) illustrates that pivotal events such as birth, puberty, marriage, ascension to a higher social class, and death define an individual's life cycle. Societies create ceremonial practices to signify these transitions or to cope with the disorientation that accompanies a new phase. Nevertheless, research indicates that among all these events, death is predominantly linked with symbols that highlight the fundamental values of a society (Rutherford and Carr, 1990). Nearly every aspect related to death, from the manner of dying to burial practices, is influenced by culture (Emke, 2002). In light of this, anthropologists during the colonial period regarded the management of death as essential for comprehending the social structure and belief systems of various societies (Metcalf and Huntington, 1991). The examination of death rituals within any culture transcends mere descriptions of the techniques used for interring human remains. It involves a thorough analysis of the social structure, cosmology, and mythology of the living culture (Arriaza, 1995). Burial rites embody the belief that human beings continue to exist after death, and the ceremonies are performed to aid the deceased in reaching their destiny in the realm of the ancestors (Beller, 2001).

In various African communities, there exists a belief that the peace, joy, and fulfilment of the deceased are contingent upon the proper execution of rites. For instance, Gehman (2008) claims that an improper burial can offend ancestral spirits and may lead to detrimental outcomes for the grieving family. In a developing nation such as Nigeria, where individuals face numerous economic difficulties, the societal expectation to allocate significant resources to honour the deceased appears to be a misallocation of priorities. The phrase "funeral-induced poverty" has recently emerged in scholarly discussions to highlight critical economic ramifications (Orden and Hirst, 2016). Families are anticipated to expend considerable sums to provide the deceased with a "befitting burial"; scholars argue that contemporary funerals have become the most elaborate, costly, and ritualised of all social events (Okaba, 1999).

The risk of households overspending on funerals across various regions has been acknowledged. Numerous studies indicate that in many areas of developing countries, the absence of funeral regulations results in household debt and social strife (Noret, 2010; La Franiere, 2011). As a result, there is a tendency for individuals to focus less on the cost of living and more on the expenses associated with dying (Mkpa, 2001). This practice is so deeply rooted that individuals prefer to save for a funeral rather than contribute to medical costs while a person is still alive. This suggests that the impoverished will have to allocate a significantly larger portion of their income to funeral expenses (Purcell and Cooper, 2015). When substantial resources are diverted from productive investments to fund extravagant events, scholars contend that honouring the deceased can lead to the financial ruin of the living (Case *et al.*, 2014). De Witte's (2003) research illustrates that the excessive costs associated with funeral practices have imposed adverse effects on the financial stability of bereaved families.

In various cultures across the globe, death is perceived as a transition from this life to

the realm of the living dead (Madu, 2012; Okwueze, 2012). Consequently, a safe passage is contingent upon the execution of certain rites by those who are grieving (King, 2013). In some cultures, burial rites are regarded as separate from funeral rites (Okeke, 2010). While burial rites refer to ceremonies associated with interment, funeral rites involve rituals performed after burial to aid the deceased in fulfilling his or her destiny (Izunwa, 2016). Regardless, the belief system within a particular society underpins the practices undertaken by the bereaved from the moment of death until the conclusion of the mourning period (Iteyo, 2009). These practices encompass rituals related to the announcement of an individual's death, mourning rituals, ritual purification, and burial rites. In light of this context, this study assesses the rites and associated ritual practices surrounding burial among the Ibil Ogoja community in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Ritual Practices

Burial rituals in Nigeria, like in many parts of Africa, are deeply rooted in cultural and religious beliefs. Nigeria's diverse ethnic landscape means that traditional burial customs differ greatly among ethnic groups, each with its own distinctive practices and rites. Nonetheless, there are common themes across most Nigerian communities that highlight respect for the dead, the continuation of life in the spiritual realm, and the significance of communal participation. Among the Yoruba people of south-western Nigeria, for instance, burial is not merely about disposing of a body but is seen as a vital process to ensure the smooth transition of the deceased into the ancestral world. The Yoruba believe in the existence of an afterlife where the deceased can continue to influence their descendants (Awolalu *et al.*, 1979). Therefore, burial rituals often involve prayers, offerings, and songs that guide the spirit of the deceased to its final resting place among the ancestors.

Similarly, in south-eastern Nigeria, the Igbo people also have elaborate burial customs that reflect their belief in life after death. For the Igbo, the dead are honoured through various rites that ensure their peaceful rest and continued positive influence on the living. The burial of an elder, in particular, is a highly revered event, marked by days of communal feasting, dances, and sacrifices (Nwoye, 2011). The family's reputation often depends on how well the funeral is conducted, as it reflects the community's respect for the deceased and the family's adherence to cultural values. In contrast, the northern Hausa-Fulani people, who are predominantly Muslim, follow Islamic burial traditions, which are simpler and less elaborate. The deceased is typically buried on the same day of death, following specific Islamic rites such as ritual washing, shrouding, and a communal prayer known as Salat al-Janazah (Smith, 1987). The simplicity of Hausa-Fulani burials reflects the Islamic teaching that all humans are equal in death, regardless of their social status in life.

Funeral rites are integral to African communities, serving both religious and social functions. They are not just about mourning the deceased but also about celebrating their life, affirming community solidarity, and reinforcing cultural values. These rites often follow a pattern of preparation, mourning, and celebration, with rituals designed to ensure the peaceful transition of the deceased to the afterlife.

Ritual behaviour is an activity full of symbols. The language of ritual is therefore said to be symbolic. However, due to the existence of various belief systems in the world, a specific interpretative model may not apply to all societies. However, several societies have put certain rites and rituals in place as marks of symbolic commemoration that introduce the

individual as he transitions to other stages of life (Bell, 1997). Some ceremonies celebrate the natural transitions that humans experience. However, every rite of passage portrays three distinctive patterns that are interrelated (Gennep, 1960). The separation phase removes the individual from normal social life. This is associated with death. The individual who dies is separated from the world of the living and takes on another form of existence. The ritual of death and burial can be considered a ritual of separation. During burial ceremonies, the grief of losing a loved one is emotionally expressed in tears.

The transition stage is marked by uncertainties where the individual undergoes preparation for a change of status. Suitability for the new status depends on the performance of the required symbolic actions. Death rituals are done to move the deceased symbolically from the state of being among the living to the state of being among the dead. Without these symbolic actions, the transactions are not made. Therefore, this stage is the preparatory phase where people are prepared for tasks, challenges and risks of their new status in the social network (Charles, 2010). The final stage of the funeral rite is the aggregation stage. This is often referred to as the stage of reintegration. It is meant to bring the deceased into the ancestral home, thereby ending the state of liminality. The deceased reintegrates into the ancestral world as he settles into his new status.

The process of separation, transition and reintegration also applies to the bereaved. The bereaved go through the reality of the pain of separation from their loved one. Once the body is buried, the bereaved go through a transition period where they recognise that their lives must go on without the deceased. The funerary rituals help the bereaved to be reintegrated into society after the period of mourning. The bereaved are expected after the process of reintegration to resume their normal duties after coming to terms with the fact of the loss of their member.

Ritual Practices involved in the Burial Ceremony

In many African societies, the dead are believed to continue to exist in the spiritual world, where they watch over and protect their descendants. As such, funeral rites are seen as essential for ensuring that the deceased is properly honoured and integrated into the ancestral world. Among the Akan people of Ghana, for example, funerals are grand affairs that involve days of feasting, drumming, and dancing. The body is often displayed in elaborate traditional attire, symbolising the status and achievements of the deceased (Buah, 1986). The funeral thus becomes a public celebration of life and a reaffirmation of the deceased's place within the community.

In South Africa, the Zulu people also have a strong tradition of elaborate funerals, particularly for important community members. The Zulu believe that the dead continue to influence the living and, therefore, must be honoured with appropriate rites. These rites include animal sacrifices, prayers, and public processions that demonstrate respect for the deceased and reinforce social cohesion (Ngubane, 1977).

One of the key elements of African funeral rites is the notion of collective mourning. Funerals are typically communal events that involve not just the family of the deceased but the entire community. This collective participation reflects the belief that the individual is part of a larger social and spiritual fabric, and the death of one person affects the entire community (Mbiti, 1969). This sense of communal responsibility is evident in the way African funerals are organised, with neighbours, friends, and extended family all playing a role in the preparations and ceremonies.

Symbolism is a critical aspect of African funerals, with each ritual act carrying deep cultural and religious meanings. These symbols are meant to facilitate the deceased's passage into the afterlife, ensure the continuity of life, and strengthen the community's bonds. One of the most prominent symbols in African funerals is the use of music and dance. In many cultures, music is not only a form of expression but a means of communication with the spiritual world. Drumming, in particular, is believed to summon the spirits and guide the soul of the deceased to its final resting place. Among the Yoruba, drummers are often invited to play at funerals to invoke the ancestors and celebrate the life of the deceased (Adeboye, 2016). The rhythmic patterns are said to mimic the heartbeat of the Earth, symbolising the continuity of life.

Animal sacrifices are another common symbol in African funerals, representing the offering of life to ensure the peaceful passage of the deceased. In many Nigerian communities, the sacrifice of animals such as cows or goats is a way to honour the deceased and appease the ancestors. This practice is particularly significant among the Igbo, who believe that the blood of the sacrificed animal purifies the soul of the deceased and helps them on their journey to the afterlife (Nwoye, 2011). The animal's life is symbolically offered in exchange for the peaceful rest of the deceased.

Burial rites are parts of the social order (Peters and Bassey, 2019b) in most African societies. In East Africa, the Maasai people of Kenya and Tanzania have a unique approach to burial that diverges from most African practices. Traditionally, the Maasai did not bury their dead but left the bodies in the open to be consumed by scavengers, reflecting their belief that burial polluted the earth (Saitoti, 1986). This practice has largely changed due to modern influences, but it illustrates the diversity of funeral customs across Africa.

Clothing and adornment also play a symbolic role in funerals. In many African cultures, the deceased is dressed in their finest attire as a sign of respect and to signify their readiness to meet the ancestors. Among the Efik of Cross River State in Nigeria, for instance, the deceased is often adorned in traditional royal garments if they were a respected elder or community leader (Okpoko, 2002). The choice of attire symbolises the deceased's social status and ensures that they are properly recognised in the spiritual world. While there are common themes in African burial practices, cultural variations abound due to the continent's vast diversity of ethnic groups and religions. Nigeria alone, with over 250 ethnic groups, presents a rich tapestry of burial customs that vary widely between regions and communities.

Regarding the specific burial customs of the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State, Nigeria, there are limited published ethnographic studies. However, oral histories and local anthropological studies can provide some insights into the burial practices of this community. The Ibil people, like many other ethnic groups in Cross River State, place significant emphasis on the proper burial of their dead, particularly elders. Local oral traditions suggest that funerals are elaborate community events that involve the extended family and neighbours, highlighting the communal nature of Ibil society. The rituals typically include wake-keeping, prayers, feasting, and animal sacrifices, similar to the customs found among neighbouring groups like the Ekoi and Efik people (Okpoko, 2002).

An important aspect of Ibil's burial practices is the belief in the ongoing influence of the dead on the living. The Ibil, like many other African communities, believe that the spirits of the deceased must be properly honoured through rituals to ensure their peaceful rest and prevent them from causing harm to the living. This belief in the active role of ancestors in daily life is reflected in the care and attention given to funeral ceremonies, where traditional

religious practices are often blended with Christian elements due to the influence of Christianity in the region. While local written sources on Ibil burial customs may be scarce, anthropologists and local historians such as Okpoko (2002) have documented similar practices among the Efik and Ekoi, which share cultural similarities with the Ibil. These communities place a high value on burial rites as a means of maintaining social harmony and ensuring the well-being of the community, a theme that resonates across many African cultures.

Among the Ijaw people of the Niger Delta, burials are elaborate affairs that involve masquerades, gun salutes, and public displays of wealth and status. The Ijaw believe that the dead deserve to be sent off in style, and funerals often become competitions for social prestige (Alagoa, 1999). This contrasts with the burial practices of the Tiv people of central Nigeria, where funerals are more modest and focused on communal mourning rather than ostentation (Udu, 2012). Religious influence also contributes to variations in burial practices. As mentioned earlier, Islamic communities such as the Hausa-Fulani in northern Nigeria follow Islamic burial rites, which emphasise simplicity and equality in death. In contrast, Christian communities, particularly in southern Nigeria, have adopted a mixture of traditional and Christian practices. For example, in the Igbo community, it is common to hold a church service for the deceased, followed by traditional burial rites that honour the ancestors and ensure the deceased's peaceful rest (Uchendu, 2008).

Scholars capture the meaning of rituals as symbolic, routine and repetitive activities through which people make connections with what is considered the most valuable dimension of life (Kyalo, 2013; Ehimuam, 2021). Thus, rituals are regarded as acts which are rife with symbolic elements rooted in the belief system of all societies (Nyamadi, 2015). As human existence is seen as a journey with a series of changes from birth to death, societies prescribe ritual acts that accompany the varied stages of the life cycle of individuals. (Nwadiokwu *et al*, 2016) According to Bell (1992), rites and rituals are instruments for social and cultural integration, appropriation, and social functions are the effects of a rite on the social structure and transformation which occur in all societies. They involve symbolic actions which reaffirm the values in society. One approach to the study of ritual emphasises the social functions of behaviour. Studies have shown that burial is more than simply a way to dispose of the dead. The issues of death bring into focus certain fundamental cultural values. For example, the work of Mogawane (2015) indicates that burial is a social act laden with meaning. The various rituals and ceremonies that are performed are primarily concerned with the explanation, validation and integration of a people's view of the world.

Ebeh (2007) affirms that most cultures think of the next world when they inter their deceased members. Since the death of a member of a group causes disturbance in the social order, the various aspects of burial practices help to bring the social group closer together (Robben, 2004). Along this line, Barrett (1988) asserts that burials are not only events for the mourning of the departed, but also for the remaking of society. Mandelbaum (1959) maintains that death ritual brings people together at moments of crisis and remind them of their responsibilities to the dead, the bereaved and to others in society. In this way, burial rites promote the solidarity of the group. Atinga (2006) adds that death brings the members of the community together and confirms the individual's membership. In attending the burial of the dead, people reinforce the link with the bereaved and with society as a whole. As a result, Radcliffe –Brown (1968) asserts that ritual helps to affirm the social bond as individuals signal their commitment to one another and to the society itself. Studies by Hertz (1960) show

that burial ritual offers a respite for society to accommodate this change and provide the opportunity for social readjustment.

Ethnographic studies offer an in-depth view (Peters and Bassey, 2019a) of funeral rituals across African tribes, revealing how these practices are rooted in cultural, religious, and social contexts. Scholars like Metuh (1987) have explored the complexity of African traditional religions, including the intricate burial customs that vary from tribe to tribe. Metuh's study on African traditional beliefs and practices provides a comparative analysis of funeral rituals across different African tribes, emphasising the symbolism and communal nature of these practices. In Metuh's (1987) exploration of funeral rituals, one of the key observations is the role of ancestors and the afterlife in shaping burial customs. Among the Igbo people of south-eastern Nigeria, for instance, funerals are a communal affair, with rites aimed at ensuring the peaceful transition of the deceased into the realm of the ancestors. The burial of an elder is marked by elaborate ceremonies that involve animal sacrifices, music, and feasting. These rituals are believed to secure the deceased's place among the ancestors, who are thought to continue influencing the living (Metuh, 1987).

Among the Ashanti of Ghana, funeral rituals similarly emphasise the deceased's journey to the spiritual realm. The Ashanti people believe in a connection between the living, the dead, and the unborn, a concept known as *Sankofa*. Funerals are therefore highly elaborate and can last several days, involving processions, drumming, and offerings to the ancestors. Metuh's (1987) study underscores the significance of funeral rites in maintaining this cyclical relationship between generations, reinforcing communal ties, and honouring the deceased. Metuh's ethnographic work highlights the symbolic use of music, dance, and sacrifice in African funerals, illustrating how these elements serve both religious and social purposes. The communal nature of African funerals is a recurring theme in these studies, as they often involve not just the family of the deceased but the entire community, reflecting a collective responsibility to honour the dead and maintain social cohesion.

Another approach to the study of ritual emphasises psychological functions of behaviour, which refers to the effects of a rite on the individual involved in the ritual (Radcliff–Brown, 1968). Malinowski (1988) maintains that burial rites function to allay anxiety, which the crisis of death has triggered. Several studies (for example, Jordan and Litz, 2014; Keyes *et al.*, 2014) allude to the link between death and mental conflict and the volatile behaviour of the bereaved. Burial rites dampened the potential danger to the individual and also prepared him for his own ultimate demise (Malinowski, 1958). The rites of passage for the dead and the bereaved are thus cultural strategies for dealing with the impact of death (Boltum, 2007).

Burial rites also serve personal functions. This view is well supported in the literature. For example, the works of Howells (1959) assert that burial rites support the individual as he moves to accomplish the proper sequence of his life cycle. To some extent, scholars believe that funerals are of more importance to the dead. It is acknowledged that death is a journey to the world of the ancestors. However, successful rite to the world of the ancestors is predicated on the performance of rites (Kuukure, 1985). If the dead were not guided into the next life, the living would not only suffer the wrath of the dead, but the dead would also be lost from the afterlife (Kastenbaum, 2004). These elaborate ceremonies are held to secure the goodwill of the dead.

Theoretical Framework

Ritual Theory

For the purpose of this study on the burial rites of the Ibil Ogoja people of Cross River State, Nigeria, Ritual Theory by Victor Turner (1969) and Émile Durkheim (1915) provides a robust theoretical lens to understand the cultural, social, and economic implications of funeral practices. Drawing on the works of Victor Turner and Émile Durkheim, the theory explores the role of rituals in maintaining social order, expressing cultural values, and mediating conflicts. Burial rites, as a key element of rituals, are integral to how societies manage the transition from life to death and negotiate communal identity, social cohesion, and status. This expanded framework outlined the major components of Ritual Theory and demonstrate how it applies to the context of Ibil burial practices, while also addressing its criticisms and limitations.

Durkheim (1915) argued that rituals serve a primary function of maintaining social cohesion within a community. In traditional African societies, rituals such as burial ceremonies bring members of the community together to collectively mourn the deceased and reaffirm their communal bonds. The mourning process is not just a private affair but a public one, reinforcing social solidarity and shared cultural values.

In the case of the Ibil Ogoja people, burial rites are deeply embedded in their cultural and religious traditions. These rites may include not only the actual burial of the deceased but also other communal activities, such as feasting, dancing, and communal prayers. The theory suggests that these rituals create a sense of "communitas" (Turner, 1969), a temporary but intense feeling of unity and equality among community members. The burial ceremony serves as a moment where social distinctions are temporarily dissolved, and the entire community participates in mourning and celebration, thereby strengthening communal bonds.

Another important element of Ritual Theory is how rituals reflect and reinforce social hierarchies. As Durkheim (1915) emphasised, rituals often serve to legitimize and perpetuate existing social structures. Burial practices, in particular, are closely tied to social status, wealth, and family reputation in many African societies, including among the Ibil Ogoja people. Elaborate funerals are often a display of family prestige and social standing. In the Ibil context, the size, opulence, and grandeur of the funeral can serve as a public expression of the family's wealth and influence. This dynamic not only elevates the status of the deceased in the afterlife but also reaffirms the family's standing within the community. As such, funerals become both a social and economic event, where families may feel pressured to spend significant amounts of money to meet community expectations and maintain their social reputation.

Ritual Theory helps explain this by positing that rituals often reflect power dynamics within a society. Those with more resources can afford more elaborate ceremonies, thereby reinforcing their higher social status. This can create social tension, as fewer wealthy families may feel pressured to match these expectations despite their financial limitations (Turner, 1969).

A critical element of Victor Turner's (1969) Ritual Theory is the concept of liminality, the transitional phase in which participants of a ritual are temporarily outside their normal social roles. In burial rites, liminality represents the in-between stage where the deceased is neither fully dead nor fully transitioned into the afterlife, and the living are engaged in a

process of adjustment. In the Ibil community, the burial rites symbolise not only the passage of the deceased but also a social transformation for the living. The family of the deceased may experience a shift in their social roles, as they move from being ordinary members of society to ones that carry the status of mourners. The rites serve to reintegrate them into the community after they have completed their mourning responsibilities, thus marking a transition back to normalcy. This transformative process is essential for both the individual and the community as it allows for the reestablishment of order and continuity after the disruption of death (Turner, 1969).

While rituals are often viewed as fostering social harmony, they can also be a source of conflict. As Turner (1969) observed, the process of ritual can sometimes expose underlying social tensions or divisions, particularly when there are competing expectations or interpretations of how the ritual should be conducted. In Ibil burial rites, for example, there may be generational or ideological divides within the family about how to honor the deceased. While older generations may prioritise traditional and elaborate ceremonies, younger family members might advocate for simpler, less costly rites, reflecting modern economic realities. These conflicts are not just about practical matters but also about deeper questions of identity, values, and tradition.

Turner's concept of "social drama" is relevant here. He posited that rituals are often stages where social conflicts are played out and, ideally, resolved. The burial ceremony thus becomes a space for negotiating these conflicts, where different factions of the family or community must come together to reach a consensus on how to honour the deceased, thereby restoring social order (Turner, 1969).

Despite its strengths, Ritual Theory has been criticised for several reasons, particularly in how it relates to complex, modern societies. One of the primary criticisms of Ritual Theory is that it tends to overemphasise the role of rituals in promoting social cohesion and harmony, often neglecting the disruptive or divisive aspects of ritual practices. In reality, as seen in many African societies, including the Ibil Ogoja community, burial rites can exacerbate social tensions, particularly when families are financially burdened by the cost of elaborate funerals. The theory does not always account for the long-term economic strain and emotional stress that such practices can place on families. For instance, while Turner's concept of *communitas* highlights the temporary equality experienced during rituals, it may not fully capture the unequal distribution of resources that often underlies these ceremonies. Wealthier families may be able to afford more elaborate funerals, which reinforces social inequality rather than dissolving it, as suggested by the theory (Schneider, 2006).

Ritual Theory primarily focuses on the symbolic and social aspects of rituals, often overlooking the material and economic realities that shape these practices. While the theory provides a rich analysis of the cultural and social functions of burial rites, it does not adequately address the economic burden that these practices impose on families. In the case of Ibil burial rites, the economic impact is a central concern. The financial strain of organising elaborate funerals can lead to long-term debt, which is not fully explained by a theory that focuses more on social harmony than on economic realities. Supplementing Ritual Theory with Political Economy Theory or Social Exchange Theory could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the material dimensions of burial rites.

Another criticism of Ritual Theory is its tendency to focus on collective social processes, often overlooking individual agency. While rituals are indeed communal events, individuals within the community may experience and interpret these practices differently. In

the case of Ibil burial practices, younger generations or economically disadvantaged family members may resist traditional expectations, advocating for simpler or more affordable ceremonies. This resistance is not always adequately captured by a theory that emphasises collective social action over individual decision-making.

Methodology

This study employed ethnographic research design. The study was conducted in Ibil community in Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the autonomous communities that make up Nkum Clan. It consists of many units such as Nkporo, Ndoh, Abrumbede, Itung, Ishaya, Ngbabila, Abontek, Ishi Aleke, Mbenkpan, Moukom, Idubum, Abarutime. Ibil is located in Nkum Clan Cluster in Ogoja Local Government Area, Cross River State. It is situated at Latitude 6.5^o or 6^o30' 27 North and Longitude 8.6^o or 8^o39'36 east. IBIL is bordered in the East by the Ekajuk Clans, in the West by the Yala Tribe, in the North by Ishibori and lastly it is bordered in South by Ekajuk Ward II (Bansara) (crossrivestate.gov.ng, 2025).

Ibil people are part of the Nkum Clusters. Other groups in the Nkum Cluster include: Ishindede, Itung, Nfamju, Ikandangha, Igodor, Aladim, Ikpagada, Ukpe. The Nkum Clan originated from Ibebed, according to one Chief Emmanuel, a native of Ibil Community. They are predominantly farmers and their crops include yams, cassava, rice, beans, okro, maize, groundnuts and oil palm. The method of agriculture is not based on mechanisation because the use of crude implements still dominates the scene. Pockets of privileged individuals use machines such as tractors to cultivate their farms, mostly swamps for rice farming. Other crops being cultivated in the community do not involve the use of machines. In this light, the mode of farming here is subsistence farming. Rice, being one of the major items produced here, is produced in enormous quantities, and the end product after harvest finds its way to Abakiliki market. The people of Ibil usually parboil their rice before taking it to the mill. Every bill or debt that accrues from the farming season is usually cleared after sales are made from farm produce. Its rice, cassava and yams are the dominant crops cultivated by both the old and young, and this forms the bulk of revenue that is generated as other crops only play complementary roles (crossrivestate.gov.ng, 2025).

The study participants selected were subjected to oral interviews from the community. The sample size determination was guided by Fusch and Creswell (2015), the criterion of saturation based on information redundancy, where sampling can be discontinued when no new information is elicited by sampling more units. The researcher was more interested in the quality of data than the number of study participants. Fatterman's (2010) big-net approach was also engaged, which describes every study participant as part of the sample size, and the total participants become the sample size of the study at the point of saturation.

Findings

Ritual Practices in Burial Ceremony

There are public ceremonies rife with symbolic practices held during burial events in order to properly commit the departed to Mother Earth. Burial rites being from the moment someone is identified as dead. Society spells out how the body is treated and disposed, and specifies the behaviour of the bereaved. These practices are done in a structured and patterned way that is similar to past performances. Emerging from observations, in-depth interviews and group discussion, various actions were highlighted as crucial cultural prescription for

interments.

According to one of the male participants involved in in-depth interview:

As soon as someone dies, observance of burial rituals begins. The immediate family makes official public announcement of the death of their member. This announcement will attract friends, neighbours and distant relative to the compound of the deceased. The bereaved and the visitors wail or scream to express their shock over the departure of their loved one. The immediate family members will keep the body of the deceased in a straight position, and ensure the eyes and mouth are closed. Anus and vagina in case of a female body, are equally blocked. After these practices, the corpse is covered with wrapper. All these preliminary activities are symbolic and they serve useful functions (Participant A, in-depth interview, 24/3/2024).

Another participant (female) during in-depth interview added that:

After all the home rituals have been concluded, the eldest son of the deceased will decide whether to embalm the body at home or deposit it in the mortuary. Meanwhile, if the dead person is a man, there will be significant changes expected in the behaviour of the surviving wife. She will detach from social gathering, recreational activities and commercial ventures. This is to enable her mourn her husband. During the mourning ritual, a widow has to shave her hair, change her cloth to black gown, and avoid wearing ornamental materials. Visitors come to see her in a sorrowful mood and console her. (Participant H, female in-depth interview, 24/3/2024).

Some discussants during FGD agreed that movement restriction and other practices imposed on widows are not strictly followed by widowers.

According to a female discussant:

When a married man dies, his wife is expected by the social group to which she belongs to demonstrate beyond doubt that she is mourning her husband. Mourning exercise is characterized by strict cultural prescriptions. But if a woman dies, society expect the husband to mourn but at the same time display his manliness and ability to endure hardness. (Discussant G, FGD female, 25/3/2024).

Another female discussant added that:

If the cause of the death of a man is considered not natural, there are ritual practices done to ascertain whether his wife's hands are stained with his blood. The woman would go through rigorous trial by ordeal including moving across the husband's corpse and swearing to an oath. If she is accepted as a good woman. If the outcome is negative, society stipulates that she is sanctioned in

line with the custom of the land. A number of sanctions such as confiscation of her husband's property and banishment. These practices are rarely applicable to men. (Discussant I, female, 24/2/24).

Discussants identify that in the midst of mourning, serious arrangement is made towards the successful hosting of the burial programme. A male discussant during FGD commended that:

As the family grieve over the loss of their loved one, the eldest son or daughter calls for a meeting. Members of the extended family are notified of the date of the meeting. The venue is always the dead man's compound. As the gather, useful suggestions on the next line of action prescribed by culture are made. Issues or any matter arising are addressed during the meeting. However, a top agenda is the drawing of financial plans for the celebration ahead. Once the budget is out, relatives, friends and well-wishers identify what they can do to support the children in carrying out the proper burial ceremony in line with culture and societal expectation (Discussant M, FGD man, 25/03/2024).

Another discussant (female) during FGD added that:

The practice of supporting the children of the deceased in offsetting financial responsibilities pertaining to the burial ceremony is based on reciprocity. If the dead person while he or she was alive, used to support others, he will reap what he sowed. This principle has made people to develop a sense of community and consciousness that whatever you give in support of the burial of another person, you are actually supporting your own burial (Discussant N, FGD (man) 24/3/2024).

A participant in in-depth interview affirmed that the idea of reciprocity attached to donation is functional. According to him:

With the understanding that huge financial responsibility that comes with burial celebration should be borne by the just the children of the deceased, extended family members, relatives, friends and even people in the community usually come and make their donations. Some people give food items or pledge to sponsor one thing or the other (participant K, In-depth interview, 25/03/2024).

From the observation of the researcher, which was corroborated during in-depth interview, there are some social sanctions attached to non-camphene. A male participant during in-depth interview commented:

“Our culture has made provision for sustaining the elaborate ceremony that accompanies burial. One of such is gift giving ritual. One of the ways to ensure that this pattern is maintained is through

social sanction. Hence, people who do not show up at all in this respect are noted for future action. Also, people that pledge to donate and at the end fail to do so are frowned at and at times their non-compliance could be a topic of informal conversation in the community (Participant J in-deth interview, 25/03/2024).

Another participant (female) highlighted the wake keeping ritual in the community. She had this to say:

A date will be fixed for burial during one of the meetings with the family. A week to the event mourning house is opened. It is a period where people can officially come to register their condolences. Local mat is spread on the floor of the deceased parlour and the bereaved family sit in a mournful position with black cloth. Within the same week, raffia tent is contributed by the kinsmen of the deceased and local alcoholic drinks are served. A night before the burial is set aside as a time for vigil and related rites at the home of the deceased. If the deceased was a church goer, the church will conduct the vigil. Church service usually last for three hours. The remaining time is spent with friends, family and community members who have gathered loud musical is presentation done and entertainment or guest is a major activity. As public entertainment continues people begin to shift their attention from the deceased to celebration (participant M, (male), in-depth interview on 24/03/2024).

Participant in in-deth interview spoke freely about the ritual cleansing exercise involved burial ceremonies in the area. A female participant asserted that:

On the day before the burial ceremony, the corpse is brought back from the mortuary to the compound where the event will take place. In the morning hours of the next day being the burial day, the body is prepared for burial by way of ceremonial washing ritual. This ritual is performed by family members who are of the same gender as the deceased. The body is handled with dignity. (Participant K, male, in-depth interview, 24/03/2024).

A participant during in-deth interview mentioned ritual practices associated with the preparation of burial site. According to him:

There are ritual practices done at the graveyard. First the eldest son of the deceased will indicate the spot where his father would be buried. If a woman dies and her husband is alive, it is the husband that will make such decision. Bottles of drink, local gin, carton of beer and a coke are demanded from the grandchildren or the family if there are no grandchildren. The eldest man will make some utterness and signal, the commencement of digging. The grave diggers will drink the hot drink and commence their work (Participant and Commence their work. (Participant J, in-deth

interview, 25/03/2024).

In the words of another participant; the eldest son or the husband is required to play a symbolic role at the graveyard.

According to him:

“The clergy conduct the service if the deceased were a Christian. At the end of the exercise, men will lower down the coffin to the grave. After laying down the remains, the eldest child or the husband, if a woman died and her husband is still alive, will be called upon to perform the symbolic sand-to-sand and dust-to-dust ritual (Participant M, in-depth interview, 26/03/2024).

Participants of the study expressed the view that ritual practices involved in burial ceremony varies inversely as the status of the deceased. One of the participants expressed the following views:

“The status of an individual in the society is a key determining factors guiding what is considered appropriate burial ritual. If the deceased was a traditional ruler, village chief, title holder, or a member of a socio-cultural society such as Ekpe, ritual practices in the event of his/her demise will reflect norms associated with his social rank. And the ritual practices will not be opened to non-initiates as in the case of Ekpe society. Under normal circumstances, the ritual practices involved I burial ceremonies will go this way. After the body is lowered down, great and colourful displays, demonstrations and entertainment begin. It would even appear that nothing sad happened (Participant P, in-depth interview, 25/03/2024)

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings revealed the ritual practices involved in burial ceremonies in the community. These include home rituals, mourning rituals, ritual cleansing and burial rituals. Valuable insight was generated from the interpretation of the participation about the ritual practices and their cultural connotations. These ritual practices are structured and are carried out in a patterned way. The report of the participant and literature reviewed in line with the objectives of the study revealed that the context of burial ritual provided a structure which embodies psychological, social, physical and spiritual components for the management of emotions of the bereaved. It is held that multiple ritual practices allowed the bereaved to channel their thoughts in ways that help them to confront the reality of death. This finding is consistent with Bottum (2007), who submitted that rituals associated with interment allowed the schemas of the bereaved to be exposed to social, cultural and religious constructed interventions.

At the community level, since the death of a member of a community causes disturbance in the social order, gathering together to perform these rituals reinforces close-knit bond among residents of a community. This finding aligns with the finding of Despelder and Strickland (2011) that burial rituals strengthen social networks as the community gathers to observe principles of culture. Similarly, the finding is in agreement with Lober *et al.*, (2006) that the symbolic actions associated with burial provide a medium for understanding

and marking social change and expressing deep emotions.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to investigate the ritual practices related to the burial customs of the Ibil-Ogoja people. This research examined the reasons behind the cultural celebration of the deceased in order to uncover the essential beliefs regarding the rituals for death and the afterlife prevalent in the region. The rituals linked to burial within the community signify a collective action aimed at returning the deceased to Mother Earth while providing solace to those who mourn.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of the study:

1. The government should regulate ritual practices among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State
2. The government should ban rituals that are anti-human in the celebration of the dead among the Ibil people in Ogoja, Cross River State.
3. The Ibil people should understand and see how to adjust to recent economic situations when it has to do with ritual for the burials of the dead.

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